

Metal Complexes of Salical-N- α -Alanino Hydroxamic Acid (Schiff Base)

M. K. GHOSH, B. SUR and A. K. CHAKRABURTTY

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700 032

Manuscript received 4 July 1978, revised 12 December 1982, accepted 9 March 1984

Schiff base, salical-N- α -alaninohydroxamic acid, (RH₂), has been prepared and its complexes with Ni(II), Cu(II), Co(II), Mn(II), Cr(III) and UO₂(II) have been isolated in the solid state. All the products are found insoluble in water or common organic solvents. The general formula for the complexes is [M(R)(H₂O)] except for the Cr(III) complex, [Cr(R)(NO₂)(H₂O)]·H₂O and the UO₂(II) complex, [UO₂(RH)₂]. Attempts have been made to characterise the complexes with the help of the magnetic moment values, reflectance visible spectra, ir spectra and thermogravimetric analysis.

THE structural skeleton of the ligand salical-N- α -alaninohydroxamic acid, (RH₂), shows its close analogy with polypeptides, the essential functional units of protein chain. Previous workers¹ found that different metal chelate complexes of glycino-hydroxamic acid with aromatic hydroxyaldehydes gave typical Schiff base complexes showing similar physical and chemical properties. α -Alanino-hydroxamic acid, an analogue of glycino-hydroxamic acid has been found to undergo condensation with salicylaldehyde to form crystalline Schiff base, which acts as a tridentate chelating ligand. Investigation of magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes formed by this tridentate ligand with various metal ions, the analysis of their thermal decomposition curves and the examinations of their visible and infrared spectra furnish enough clues to decide the nature of bonding and possible structure of these complexes.

Experimental

The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes were determined by a Gouy's balance, using mercury tetrathiocyanatocobalt(III)²⁻⁴ as the calibrant. A Chevenard's thermobalance, type 3, A.D.A.M.E.L., Paris, was used to record thermal analysis curves upto 700°. Reflectance spectra of the complexes were taken in the solid state with a Beckman DK-2 unit employing freshly prepared MgO as reference. Infrared spectra were taken in nujol with the help of a Perkin-Elmer 337 IR spectrophotometer equipped with potassium chloride optics.

Preparation of α -alaninohydroxamic acid :

Dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed through absolute alcohol (200 ml) in a three necked flask until saturation. Dry α -alanine (50 g) was added to it and refluxed on a steam bath with continued stream of hydrogen chloride gas until the α -alanine went into solution. Refluxing was continued for 4 hr more under the same condition. α -Alaninoethyl ester was prepared from the α -alaninoethyl ester

hydrochloride obtained as above with the help of sodium ethoxide to a phenolphthalein end point. The sodium chloride formed was filtered off and α -alaninoethyl ester was taken in a conical flask with an air tight stopper.

Hydroxylamine was prepared from hydroxylaminehydrochloride (17.5 g) in the same way as that of α -alaninoethyl ester. The free hydroxylamine base was then added slowly to α -alaninoethyl ester in cold. The mixture was taken in an air tight stoppered flask was kept in a refrigerator avoiding all possibilities of the entry of moisture into the flask. White crystals of α -alaninohydroxamic acid separated out after 48 hr. It was recrystallised from acetone-water mixture (1 : 1). (Found : C, 34.21 ; H, 7.81 ; N, 26.68. Calcd. for C₉H₉O₂N₂ ; C, 34.61 ; H, 7.69 ; N, 26.93%).

Preparation of salical-N- α -alaninohydroxamic acid :

A mixture of α -alaninohydroxamic acid (10.4 g) dissolved in warm alcohol, and distilled salicylaldehyde (10 ml) was warmed in a steam bath with constant stirring. Light yellow crystals formed which were filtered, washed with alcohol and water. The crude product was recrystallised from hot alcohol and finally dried over fused calcium chloride, m.p. 138°. (Found : C, 57.32 ; H, 5.52 ; N, 13.41. Calcd. for C₁₀H₁₂O₃N₂ ; C, 57.69 ; H, 5.77 ; N, 13.46 %).

The reagent was found to be insoluble in water but soluble in common organic solvents like alcohol, acetone, toluene, dioxane and pyridine. It could be dissolved in dilute alkali without decomposition. However, treatment with dilute acids caused its decomposition. It gives characteristic violet colour reaction with ferric chloride solution.

Preparation of the metal complexes :

Though salical-N- α -alaninohydroxamic acid could be isolated in the free state as a solid, the complexes

TABLE 1—ANALYSES AND PROPERTIES OF METAL CHELATES

Tentative formula	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				% Loss of water at 110° Found/(Calcd.)	μ_{eff} at 304K B.M.
		Metal	Carbon	Nitrogen	Hydrogen		
[Ni(R)(H ₂ O)]·2.5H ₂ O	Bluish white	18.32 (17.92)	36.41 (36.63)	8.40 (8.55)	5.06 (5.19)	13.40 (13.94)	2.72
[Cu(R)(H ₂ O)]3H ₂ O	Green	18.95 (18.61)	34.91 (35.14)	7.91 (7.83)	5.13 (5.27)	15.69 (15.81)	1.72
[Co(R)(H ₂ O)]3H ₂ O	Reddish brown	17.01 (17.48)	35.88 (35.62)	7.93 (8.31)	5.30 (5.34)	16.16 (16.03)	3.72
[Cr(R)(NO ₂)(H ₂ O) ₂]·2H ₂ O	Grey	13.65 (13.26)	30.42 (30.61)	10.87 (10.71)	4.41 (4.59)	9.34 (8.97)	3.57
[Mn(R)(H ₂ O)]H ₂ O	Pale yellow	18.21 (18.41)	40.61 (40.22)	8.98 (9.42)	4.62 (4.71)	5.98 (6.06)	2.56
[UO ₂ (RH) ₂]	Orange	35.21 (34.79)	34.32 (35.09)	8.44 (8.18)	3.08 (3.22)	—	Diamag- netic

TABLE 2—SOME CHARACTERISTIC IR VIBRATION (cm⁻¹) OF SCHIFF BASE OF α -ALANYLHYDROXAMIC ACID AND SALICYLALDEHYDE AND ITS METAL COMPLEX

Ligand	[Ni(R)H ₂ O]	[Cu(R)H ₂ O]	[CoR(H ₂ O)]	[MnR(H ₂ O)]	[Cr(R)(NO ₂) ₂ H ₂ O]	[UO ₂ (RH) ₂]	Band assignment
3200	3300	3200, 3100	3225	3150	3330	3200	ν_{OH} — H-bonded
2900-2800	2800-2900	2900-2800	2910-2850	2900-2800	2960-2850	2900	ν_{C-H} vibration
1670	1650	1640	1638	1655-1625	1650	1625	$\nu_{C=N}$ stretching
1600	1620	1600	1602	—	—	1600	$\nu_{C=O} + \nu_{C=N}$
	1640	1530	1536	1550	1545	1520	rocking vibration of H ₂ O molecules
1460-1440	1460	1460-1440	1470-1452	1460-1440	1458-1452	1460	OH ₂ deformation molecule
1370	1370	1370-1380	1380	1360	1365	1380	δ_{CH_2}
1295-1240	1310-1270	1310-1270	1302-1272	1330-1240	1300-1480	1300-1270	δ_{OH}
1220	1170	1190	1220, 1190	1210, 1180	1200	1240-1185	ν_{C-O} (phenolic)
1180, 1160	1170	1150, 1190	1155, 1190	1180-1210	1154, 1200	1185, 1150	$\nu_{as}(C=N)$
1110-1085	1120	1130-1110	1135-1120	1120-1105	1132-1110	1110	O—H in plane vitral
1040-1005	1040	1020	1038	1030-1020	1035	1040, 1010	Pr-OH ₂
985	920	970	980-912	980, 970, 910	975-918	985	ν_{N-O}
900-895	895-880	890	860	900-895	905	890	$\nu_{as}C-C-N$
						865, 915	UO ₂ ²⁺
					1452		
					1280		NO ₂
					805		

described herein were prepared by adding the right proportion of the metal acetate solution in aqueous alcohol to the solution obtained by refluxing (2 hr) a mixture of α -alaninohydroxamic acid (19 g) and salicylaldehyde (1.2 ml) in aqueous ethanol in a steam bath and then refluxing the total mixture for 2 hr more. For the chromium(III) complex, instead of acetate, aquo pentamino chromium nitrate⁵ (3.4 g) was used. The complexes formed were all obtained in the solid state. They were filtered, washed repeatedly with water and alcohol and dried over fused calcium chloride.

All the compounds were found insoluble in water, alcohol, dioxane, toluene, nitrobenzene and chloroform but soluble in pyridine. They lost their water of crystallisation, if any, when heated at 110° for 2 hr.

Analysis and properties of the metal chelates are given in Table 1.

Discussion

From analogy with other hydroxamic acids⁶ and from ir frequencies^{7,8} (Table 2) salical-N- α -alanino-

hydroxamic acid may be assumed to have either of the following two possible structures having three sites of coordination thereby acting as a tridentate ligand.

The ir frequencies together with their possible interpretation are given in Table 2. The bands at 3200 cm⁻¹ of the ligand which may arise out of the stretching vibrations of phenolic -OH groups and >N-OH group are considerably shifted in all the complexes indicating their involvement in chelate formation. Apart from this, the $\nu_{(C-O)}$ phenolic and $\nu_{(N-O)}$ ^{7,8} bands at 1220 and 985 cm⁻¹ are also lowered which further supports the participation of both the phenolic -OH and the N-OH group in the formation of the complexes. Again, two characteristic vibrations at 1670 and 1185-1160 cm⁻¹, which are due $\nu_{s}(C=N)$ and $\nu_{as}(C=N)$, respectively⁷ (aldimino, may be hydroxomato >C=N-OH) are

also shifted to lower frequency showing that nitrogen of $-\text{HC}=\text{N}$ group and probably of the hydroxamic acid group takes part as $\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{O}$ in the complex formation. However, the lowering of $\nu_{(\text{N}-\text{O})}$ conclusively supports the participation on $\text{N}-\text{OH}$ group. Thus the ligand usually behaves as a diprotic tridentate ligand in all the complexes either in the form A or B. In the UO_2^{2+} complex, however, there is a band around 3200 cm^{-1} showing the presence of free $-\text{OH}$ group in the complex which may be phenolic $-\text{OH}$ or $\text{N}-\text{OH}$. Again, the fact that the band at 1220 cm^{-1} due to phenolic $\nu_{(\text{C}-\text{O})}$ has been shifted and the band at 985 cm^{-1} due to $\nu_{(\text{N}-\text{O})}$ is hardly affected, though there is shift in $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{N})}$ and $\nu_{\text{as}(\text{C}=\text{N})}$, can hardly be justified if the bands are assigned for $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{N})}$ in $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{O})}$. It may therefore be assumed that in the case of UO_2^{2+} complex the oxime $\text{N}-\text{OH}$ group remains free and the ligand is in the form of $\text{C}-\text{NHOH}$ in the complexes. The UO_2^{2+} complex also shows the characteristic bands at 915 and 865 cm^{-1} which are due to UO_2^{2+} cation⁸. The chromium complex shows additional bands⁸ at 1452 , 1280 and 805 cm^{-1} which reveals the bidentate nature of the NO_2^- ion. All the complexes except UO_2^{2+} complex show bands at 3350 to 3500 cm^{-1} and at 1520 - 1560 cm^{-1} which are due to coordinated water molecules⁹.

The paramagnetic bluish white nickel complex has a magnetic moment of 2.72 B.M. suggesting an octahedral stereochemistry of the complex. The slightly lower value indicates orbital contribution. The element analysis shows that the complex has a molecular formula $[\text{Ni}(\text{R})\text{H}_2\text{O}]\cdot 2.5\text{ H}_2\text{O}$. Loss of water at 110° corresponds to $2.5\text{ H}_2\text{O}$ per molecule which may be assumed to be water of crystallisation. Hence the skeleton formula of the complex is $[\text{NiR}-\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. A tetrahedral stereochemistry with the ligand occupying three coordination positions and the water molecule in the remaining one, has been precluded because such a system will have higher magnetic moments. The visible spectra also show bands around 24390 and 16500 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ and ${}^3\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3\text{T}_{1g}$ octahedral stereochemistry. Probably the ligand behaves as a tetradentate one in this case utilising its free $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group giving rise to a polymeric octahedral structure for the $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ complex. This is supported by the shifting of $\nu_{(\text{C}=\text{O})}$ band at 1600 cm^{-1} in the case of $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ complex by $\sim 20\text{ cm}^{-1}$. So, an octahedral stereochemistry seems plausible for the $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ complex. Assignment of tetrahedral disposition to strictly four coordinated $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ complexes merely on the basis of their paramagnetic nature have been questioned and information summarised by Koshits⁹ shows that many paramagnetic $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ complexes once thought to be tetrahedral are in reality effectively six coordinated in the solid state.

The magnetic moment of 1.72 B.M. for the $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complex together with its band at 14300 cm^{-1} region in the visible spectra due to typical square planar transition supports a planar arrangement of the ligand around the $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ ion, the three positions

being occupied by the ligand and the remaining fourth position being taken up by a water molecule.

The cobalt complex has a magnetic moment of 3.72 B.M. This, together with visible spectra showing the bands around 7200 and 16700 cm^{-1} region, which may arise out of ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \leftarrow {}^4\text{A}_g$ and ${}^4\text{T}_1(\text{P}) \leftarrow {}^4\text{A}_g$ transitions, support a tetrahedral stereochemistry of the complex where the ligand is tridentate, the remaining position being taken by a water molecule.

The grey $\text{Cr}(\text{III})$ complex has the composition $\text{Cr}(\text{R})(\text{NO}_2)\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. On heating to 110° two molecules of water are lost but the other two molecules are removed only at 220° when the complex is also completely decomposed to oxide. From ir data the nitrate group appears as bidentate and the ligand occupies three positions. So the complex be either 7 coordinated or one of the two molecules of water is coordinated (which are not removed at 110°) to chromium and the remaining one is attached with the NO_2 of the six coordinated complex by some sort of hydrogen bonding and cannot be removed at 110° . Considering that there is hardly any 7 coordinated $\text{Cr}(\text{III})$ complex, the complex may be assumed to be octahedral having six coordination. The visible spectral bands due to ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ appearing in the 24800 and 37500 cm^{-1} region, respectively also support the octahedral configuration. However, the band around 17000 cm^{-1} was not sharp enough for consideration.

The visible spectra of $\text{Mn}(\text{II})$ complex as obtained were not distinct enough to assign any configuration. The $\text{Mn}(\text{II})$ low spin octahedral complexes are generally pink while those with tetrahedral configuration having high magnetic value are generally yellow-green¹⁰. Though the compound is pale yellow in colour the magnetic moment of 2.56 B.M. is much lower than the value obtainable for tetrahedral or square planar configuration. However, the value is higher than that of octahedral one. This rather suggests the complex to be a mixture of octahedral and tetrahedral ones.

In the case of UO_2^{2+} complex, ligands behave as monoprotic bidentate chelating agents. This together with the diamagnetic nature of the complex points towards an octahedral stereochemistry for the complex.

The thermal decomposition studies of all the complex show that excepting the $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ one, all others are decomposed to their oxides without the formation of any intermediate products. In the case of the $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ complex a break is observed indicating the formation of an intermediate product in the 240 to 400° range. By assaying the loss in weight, the composition of this product is found to tally with $\text{Cu}(\text{II})$ salicylaldehyde component.

The substances being insoluble in water or in common organic solvents, the conductance measurements could not be undertaken.

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